

Agritourism: Supplementary Business for Farmers in Maharashtra State

S. G. Walke¹ and Atul Kumar²

¹Director, SNG Institute of Management and Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

²Assistant Professor, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Walke, S. G. and Kumar, Atul (2015), "Agritourism: Supplementary Business for Farmers in Maharashtra State", *MERC Global's International Journal of Social Science & Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 6, pp. 480-485.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: September 08, 2015, Revision received: September 20, 2015, Accepted: September 28, 2015

ARTICLE TYPE: Research paper

ABSTRACT

This study was designed for Maharashtra farmers interested in developing new or expanding existing Agritourism centre as a supplementary income source. This paper depicts the basic concept of "Agritourism", provides analysis of existing studies, analyses three case studies of Agritourism centres and makes recommendations for farmers for further developing Agritourism as an income stream to complement other income-generating activities. This study describes and analyses farm projects that offer Agritourism. Some major issues emerge: 1) The centers with different facilities described are located in rural areas near to large urban areas are necessary; 2) Personal satisfaction of tourists through Agripreneurs and employees with their work is important; 3) Conserving the unique character and authenticity of the center is attractive to tourists; 4) Staff with effective people skills is significant; 5) Each Agritourism centre seeks participative ways to educate the public about their products and services and 6) Different marketing strategies to make aware and promote Agritourism centres to the urban people are important.

KEYWORDS: Agritourism, Agripreneurs, U-picking, Agritouristic potential, Agritourism network.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agri-tourism is the practice of attracting travellers or visitors to an area or areas used primarily for agricultural purposes. Agri-tourism is defined by the American Farm Bureau Federation (2004) as "Agritourism refers to an enterprise at a working farm, ranch or agricultural plant conducted for the enjoyment of visitors that generates income for the owner. It refers to the act of visiting farms or any agricultural, horticultural, or agribusiness operations for the purpose of enjoyment, education, or active involvement in the activities of the farm or operation that also adds to the economic viability of the site.

Agri-tourism is a way of enduring tourist development and multi-activity in rural areas through which the visitor has the opportunity to get aware of agricultural areas, agricultural occupations, local products, traditional food & the daily life of the rural people, as well as the cultural elements and traditions. Barbieri and Mshenga (2008) define Agritourism as "any practice developed on a working farm with the purpose of attracting visitors". McGehee, Kim and Jennings (2007) explains Agritourism as "rural enterprises which incorporate both a working farm environment and a commercial tourism component"

1.1. Different modes of Agritourism in Maharashtra

- **Farm stays:** The activity of visiting a farm for overnight stays and for the purpose of participating in or enjoying farm activities and/or other attractions offered.
- **Farm visits:** The activity of visiting a farm for short periods of time for the purpose of participating in or enjoying farm activities and/or other attractions offered.

- **Roadside stands:** Also known as farm stands, refers to any activity where the farmer sells agricultural and value-added products from his farm directly to consumers at a stand or kiosk located on or near his farm or along a road near the farm.
- **U-pick or pick-your-own operations:** These are the fruits and farms or orchards where the customers themselves harvest the fruits or products. The prices they pay for the volume harvested will be usually higher than what the grower would get from a broker.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the research was to highlight Agritourism characteristics, Agritouristic potential of rural areas of Maharashtra and the benefits of Agritourism to the different stakeholders. Other complementary objectives pursued in this study are:

- Knowing Agroclimatic Agritourism trends in Maharashtra;
- Enlisting the Prominent Components for the development of Agritourism through the viewpoint of tourists.
- Studying the importance of utilising local resources in Agritourism;
- To prioritise the marketing tactics for Agritourism centres.

3. METHODS

The research methodology involved both the desk research and the field research, which was used to depict the concept of Agritourism and the various facets that are involved in the successful development of Agritourism. For the field research, a structured questionnaire was used to gather information from tourists comprising of both open-ended questions as well as close-ended questions. The sample size used for the study was 150. The respondents were selected by a convenient method, and the Agri-tourism Centre (ATC) owners were personally interviewed by the Researcher. Additionally, discussions were also held with the Shri. Pandurang Taware (Director, Sales and Marketing ATDC) Dr. Manohar Ingale (MIT, Kothrud) and Dr. S. S. Thigale (Symbiosis, Pune) to understand the different aspects of Agritourism, government policies, etc. The subject is vast, Researcher has limited the study to the projects at Rajuri ATC, Junnar, Pune (Parashar Agritourism Center), Chincholi Morachi ATC, Shirur Pune (Anand Agritourism Center) and Aabloli, Guhagar, Ratnagiri (Garva Agritourism Center).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Agripreneur's reasons to enter in Agritourism

Agriculture faces significant challenges in responding to the changing global Agri-business milieu. Due to the decreased incomes in agriculture in the last few decades, farm diversification is frequently recommended as one approach to business survival. The majority of farmers choose Agritourism enterprises to develop an additional source of income to their traditional agricultural practices. Over the past century, farming has become more technologically advanced than ever before. In turn, many small-scale farmers, due to economies of scale have been forced out of the industry completely or have found alternative sources of revenue. Thus, many small-scale farmers have found farm tourism to be an efficient means to supplement their declining farm incomes, while still running their valued farming operation. Other farmers have completely abandoned their traditional farming processes because the profits from their Agritourism business vastly outweigh those of their previous operation. The urban population is increasing day by day all over India and no doubt more in Maharashtra. As per census record 2011, the state has 45.23 percent urban populations, much higher than the national average of 31.16 percent. Of the 11,23,72,972 people counted in the state, 6,15,45,441 are in rural and 5,08,27,531 in urban areas.

Today the urban people's world is restricted in closed-door flats, offices, clubs, television, video games, fast food, computer, internet, and so on. They can see nature only on television or on the screen of the computers. Many people from the city right from their birth living in the city and are having a strong desire to stay in the village to live & experience rural life. These peoples want to enjoy rural life, but there is problem with various facilities. Hence, it is an opportunity for the farmers for the development of the Agri-tourism centres and to add one surest source of income. Presenting utilisation of Basic Principles of Agri-Tourism at Individual Agritourism centres:

- **It has something for tourists to see:** Animals, birds, farms, the culture of the village, dress and festivals.
- **Have something for tourists to do:** Participating in agricultural operations, riding horse, buffalo, cooking and participating in the rural games
- **Have something for tourists to buy:** rural crafts, fresh vegetables, food are few items.

Anand ATC, Shirur	Parashar ATC, Junnar	Garva ATC, Ratnagiri
1) National Bird Peacock 2) Farm scenery 3) Visit to Nighoje: Asia's largest Potholes 4) Beautiful nature	1. Well developed agricultural farm. 2. Different fruit crops, vegetables, flowers, grains, pulses & fodder crops. 3. Different irrigation system, farm-lake 4. Beautiful sunrise & sunset from 'Machan' 5. Cow buffalo, sheep, Goat rearing 6. Beautiful nature 7. Bird observation 8. Village structure, administration, credit structure, cooperative structure, NDDDB award winner Milk Dairy 9. Weekly Markets 10. Forest visit & lunch 11. Jatra Festival 12. Visit to historic and holy places like Shivneri fort, Ozar & Lenyadri Ashtavinayak Darshan, ancient temples 13. For overnight stay a quality event of Maharashtrian folk such as Jagaran, Gondhal, Powada, Bharud, Bhajan.	1) Konkan village, 2) Crops-Rice, Turmeric, Nachani 3) The Farms have Machaan and greenery all around - with mango/cashew, coconut, Jackfruit and other trees 4) Hedavi, Tavsale and Rohile Beach Experience. 5) An opportunity to see 100 years ago the house
1) Feeding to animals; Opportunity to pet or care for animals 2) Milking of cows 3) Drinking of fresh milk 4) Bullock cart riding 5) Watching rabbits	1. Inhale fresh air at 'Sanitarium of India' 2. Playing traditional games such as Ningorcha, Vitti Dandu, Bhovara, the creation of agricultural tools by hand. 3. Plantation of trees 4. Celebration of your special events	1. Fisheries, Fish hunting 2. Perform seasonal activities on the farm such as plowing, harrowing, sowing, reaping, etc. 3. Celebration of tourists special events
1) Fresh Maharashtra cuisine "Pithala-Bhakari" 2) Maharashtra Chatani, pickle of mango, sweet dish	1. "Maswadi" a popular dish of Junnar	1. Regional food and drinks (Rice, fish, Modak, Coconut water)

To experience and enjoy the above activities at any ATC different packages are available varying from Rs.500-Rs.2100 which allows tourists to stay from one day to three days.

4.2. The income of Agripreneurs before and after beginning ATC

ATC/Income	Anand and Shirur	Parashar and Junnar	Garva and Guhagar
Before	10,000 Rs	5,000 Rs	8,000 Rs
After	35,000Rs	20,000 Rs	20,000Rs

Agripreneurs indicated that their families owned small farms, utilised farming as a secondary income source, and indicated their most popular Agritourism activities are farm stays, pick-your-own produce, Celebration of special events and on-farm festivals for tourists.

4.3. Findings from tourists survey

The centres which are at an accessible distance from populated cities are succeeding to attract more tourists who prefer to stay one day or return in one day. If the centre is far away, tourists prefer to stay for more than 2 days. Since Anand ATC, Chincholi Morachi has been just 60Km from Pune city tourists from being interested to return in one day or stay for a single day after enjoying the nature and farm activities; Most of the tourists coming to Parashar ATC, Rajuri stays for 1 or 2 days whereas those visiting Garva Center, Aabloli from Mumbai or Pune stay 2-3 days.

Figure 1: Flow chart showing the connectivity of tourists to ATC's

Figure 2 reports the ways by which tourists were informed about the Agritourism centres. Obviously, word of mouth is the most important source of advertising available to those involved in Agritourism enterprises.

Figure 2: A pie chart showing Information source to know about Agritourism centre

Figure 3, then the preference of tourists, showing Prominent Components of Agritourism. Above figure clearly states the importance of different elements of Agritourism. Enjoying the scenery is the most prominent factor for Agritourism development.

Figure 3: Bar chart reflecting the importance of prominent components of Agritourism

The potential benefits of Agritourism development extend to farmers, rural communities, tourists and tourism operators.

- **Benefits for farmers:** For farmers, Agritourism is a potential way of:
 - Increasing the long term sustainability for farm businesses ;
 - Using farm-based products in new and innovative ways;
 - Improving farm revenue streams;
 - Developing new consumer market niches;
 - Increasing awareness of local agricultural products;
 - Improving farm living conditions, working areas and farm recreation opportunities
 - Developing managerial skill and entrepreneurial spirit; and
- **Benefits for communities:** From a community perspective, Agritourism can be a vehicle for:
 - Generating additional revenue for local businesses and services for tourists;
 - Stimulating the upgrade of local facilities and services
 - Increasing the protection of rural landscapes and natural environments for tourists and residents;
 - Helping preserve and revitalise local traditions, art and craft;
 - Promoting inter-regional, intercultural communication and understanding; increasing awareness of agricultural issues and values among the public;
 - Promoting the ongoing use of local agricultural products and services;
 - Helping to diversify and strengthen the rural economy via job and income creation; and
- **Benefits for tourism operators:** From a tourism industry viewpoint, Agritourism can be a means of:
 - Diversifying the mix of tourism products and services available to tourists;
 - Increasing tourism flows in attractive rural regions;
 - Increasing season length during traditionally off-peak business periods;
 - Uniquely positioning rural regions in key tourism markets; and
 - Bringing more non-local currency to local businesses
- **Benefits for tourists:**
 - Unique and authentic experience
 - Getaway from everyday stress
 - Chance to participate and see how their food is grown
 - To experience the culture and heritage

5. CONCLUSION

The gist of Case studies: Critical success factors to start and develop Agritourism Center

The three case studies described above were selected to represent distinctive types of centres offering different Agritourism experiences. Despite the range of businesses, services offered, varied locations and the different character of the centre, these cases share some common characteristics:

- **Location:** For each of these case studies, accessible location to a large city is important to attract visitors. Each has found ways to tap into existing flows of traffic, local events and festivals and to cooperate with other local businesses to bring in customers. All also take advantage of a variety of other nearby tourist attractions that help to bring tourists to the Agritourism centres.
- **Interpersonal skills:** The people involved (owners or employees) with each of these Centers are enthusiastic about their business and about working with visitors. Those attending to tourists directly are well informed and passionate about the Agritourism business. Establishing rapport with tourists, engaging them in conversation and getting them to taste the local food are all strategies used to gain the interest of tourists and to entertain them a full day.
- **Preserving Genuineness:** Each of the centres described above has a unique feature that is expressed through many aspects of the business: in the history of the place, site or region, in the layout and presentation of the facilities, in the products, in the way visitors are received, and attitudes and behaviour of farmers and their families toward the tourists. Staying true to this individual character creates a consistent and authentic image of the centres. The distinctive character and feel is an important attraction for tourists.
- **Tourists education:** In each of these cases, considerable time and effort are put into describing different activities. Learning from the agri-tourism centre about how products are

grown or made is crucial to tourists. Every centre allows tourists time to participate in different fieldwork or activities and ask questions. During visits, considerable time and energy are spent telling tourists about the lives and histories of the local people, tradition, crops, festivals, places, etc. All the Agripreneurs made available detail information about their centre in writing - in a brochure and/or on a website including all services they offer. It is likely that tourists retell the stories/information when they return home to their friends and family. This retelling at home can reinforce a positive memory about the visit, make a strong connection with the centre and can lead to return visits and additional tourists.

- **Marketing:** Each of these centres has a different target market that is based on their location, set of products and services and the vision for their business. Each centre budgets for marketing. Each reserve time to talk with tourists: to cultivate their interest in the centre. In most cases, cooperating with other businesses and agencies that promote tourism and agriculture contribute to continued business success. Word of Mouth is supreme to attract tourists to the centre.

Hence, a critical factor strongly connected with success in Agritourism businesses is the attitudes and behaviour of farmers and their families toward the tourists.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are provided for individual Farm owners who are interested in developing the new Agritourism centre:

- Take training about Agritourism through MART.
- Conduct a feasibility study to review the potential for Agritourism at your site;
- Conserve the integrity and unique character of the centre;
- Plan facilities and services with care;
- Address people-related issues;
- Attend to regulatory, licensing and insurance requirements; and
- Connect to an Agritourism network.

7. REFERENCES

1. 'Indian Economic Growth: Can it Translate into Rural Prosperity?', The Analyst, Special Issue on Agri-Business, August, 2007.
2. Bramwell, B. (1994), "Rural Tourism and Sustainable Rural Tourism", *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, Vol. 2, Issue 1-2, pp.1-6.
3. Bruch, Megan (2004), "Promotion Strategies for Agri Tourism: Agri-Unlocking Your Potential", CPA Workshop Excerpt.
4. Christ, Costas (2011), World Travel & Tourism Council's Publication Tourism for Tomorrow winners and finalists, pp. 3.
5. Dan, Bernardo; Luc, Valentin and John, Leatherman (2004), "Agritourism: If We Build It, Will They Come?", *Kansas State University Research Publication*.
6. Getz, D. and Carlsen, J. (2000), "Characteristics and Goals of family and owner-operated businesses in the rural tourism and hospitality sectors", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 21, pp. 547-560.
7. Holly, George and Ellie, Rilla (2015), "Marketing Strategies for Agritourism operations", *ANR Publication*, pp. 8444.
8. Taware, Pandurang (2007), *Krishi Paryatan*, pp. 2-7.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Dr. S. G. Walke is B.Pharm., MBA, SET and Ph.D. He is currently working as a Director in S. N. G. Institute of Management and Research, Rajgurunagar, approved by AICTE, New Delhi, Govt. of Maharashtra and affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune. He is having more than 17 years of academic and industrial experience. Symbiosis International University awarded a Ph.D. to him in February 2014 after successful completion of research work on the "Study of Agritourism Industry in Maharashtra". He is Editor in Chief of the biannual Research journal titled "National Journal of Research in Marketing, Finance and HRM" title verified by RNI and bearing ISSN no 2455-5398. He is Chief Consultant for Anand Agri Tourism Center, Morachi Chincholi. He is also contributing to the Solar Energy field by shouldering the responsibility as chief advisor to New Solar Technology, central Govt. (MNRE) approved organization, Pune. He has presented and/or published number of Research papers in varied International & National Seminars/Conferences and can be reached at krishnawalke@yahoo.co.in.

Atul Kumar is B.Sc., MBA, M.Phil. and PGDIB. He is currently working as an assistant professor in Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra, which is affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune.